

The summer assemblage of spiders in a Nantucket sandplain grassland and heathland habitat

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Abstract

We collected spiders in a Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative (NBI) 10-hectare biodiversity plot of sandplain grassland and heathland habitat on Nantucket Island to record an accurate list of species. We used sweep netting, ground collecting and pitfall trapping as collection methods. We set pitfalls in another area of grassland 800 meters from the site with a different management history. We caught a total of 777 identifiable spiders representing 85 species. Within the NBI plot we captured 69 species and completed 43 hours of hand collecting. The second pitfall trap site was surrounded by significantly different vegetation and there were several species that showed significant differences in their abundances between the two sites. We conclude that the survey is still not complete but that it is a good representation of the spider species present during the summer months in sandplain grassland and heathland. Using our data, we estimate that 20 traps set for one week in the habitat will catch 92% of the available species.

Caveat: Many of the species identifications reported here have not yet been verified and some may change as the collection is checked for errors.

Introduction

In 2006, with support from the Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative (NBI) and the Maria Mitchell Association (MMA) we began biodiversity surveys for spiders on Nantucket, Tuckernuck, and Muskeget Islands. By early 2007 we had identified 206 potential species on Nantucket and compiled basic species lists for four main habitats on the island including coastal dune, sandplain grassland and heathland, scrub oak and pitch pine forest, and hard wood forest (Mckenna-Foster and Beaton 2007). As we expected, our surveys of these habitats were incomplete. Because many spiders are cryptic and inhabit microhabitats from leaf litter to canopy, to compile an accurate species list for a habitat requires the collection of thousands of specimens through hundreds of collection hours (Coddington *et al.* 1991; Scharff *et al.* 2003). Additionally, spider communities vary with season so the ideal survey must collect for an entire year.

In 2007, with more support from NBI and MMA we organized a project to compile an accurate species list for the rare sandplain grassland and heathland habitat. We chose this habitat because its globally rare status demands we act quickly to understand the ecosystem processes associated with it. As more of these grasslands are

lost along North America's coasts to development, natural plant succession, and invasive species, an understanding of what organisms depend on them becomes more and more important. Spiders are good indicators of ecosystem health because they are generalist arthropod predators, they are highly mobile and they respond quickly to environmental change (Wise 1993; Marc *et al.* 1999). Because spiders are so important, their species lists, correlated with the effort used to compile them, can be used to document change over time within habitats.

Study Sites

We chose a square, one-hectare sample site of sandplain grassland and heathland in the Smooth Hummocks Coastal Preserve's (SHCP) 10-hectare biodiversity plot (hereafter NBI plot) (Map 1). We located the site in an area that was burned in 2004 and contained about 60% grassland and 40% woody shrubs (*Gaylussacia baccata*, *Vaccinium angustifolium*) by area (visual estimation). The UTM coordinates for the southwestern corner of the plot are 19T 0406109N 4567028E NAD27. The plot was oriented at a 60° angle from magnetic north.

We also collected in an area of SHCP predominated by sandplain grassland that was burned in 2002 (hereafter 2002 burn site) about 800 meters south of the NBI plot (Map 1). We only set pitfall traps and did not do any hand collecting in this area. The first pitfall trap was located at UTM 19T 405817N 4566668E NAD 27 and the trap line ran at approximately 110° from magnetic north.

Methods

Initial planning

Our goal was to create a species list that included some estimate of error to quantify how successful we were. Determining how accurate a species list is can be very difficult and requires a measurement of capture effort for each specimen. Scharff *et al.* (2003) suggests that for a complete survey in an eastern North American beech forest, the number of specimens collected should be about 30 times the number of species (this is called the sampling intensity). Since there is less habitat to sample in a grassland compared to a forest, we chose a lower sampling intensity of 10, which was originally proposed by Coddington *et al.* (1991) for a tropical forest. In 2006, we caught 55 species in a sandplain grassland and heathland habitat on Nantucket and to estimate how many spiders we would need to catch in 2007 to achieve a sampling intensity of 10, we multiplied the 55 species by 10 to arrive at 550 spiders. We rounded that up to 600 and, based on our experience in 2006 of catching about 10 spiders per hour during hand collections, we estimated that in 2007 we would need to collect for 60 total hours within one hectare of grassland to reach 600 specimens. We would supplement this with pitfall trapping and casual collections as well.

Hand Collections

We designed the hand collecting methods to sample the entire available spider habitat in the NBI plot. Following methodology proposed by Coddington (1991) and Scharff *et al.* (2003), collectors used sweep nets and ground searching. Each collector collected in a straight line for one hour from a randomly assigned point on the border of the plot. We started from a different border each subsequent collection interval by moving counter-clockwise around the plot to the next border. We also sampled the two solitary trees in the plot with a beatsheet for 15 minutes and extracted spiders from 13.6L of leaf litter we collected from several locations in the plot.

Sweep netting was standardized by defining a 'sweep event' as the completion of five passes with the net on one side of the collecting line. A collector completed one sweep event on each side of the collecting line before moving forward and repeating. Collectors moved between 1.5-2 meters forward to avoid re-sampling vegetation and we asked them to count their sweep events. Ground searching involved crawling along the ground and collecting every visible spider. We instructed collectors to brush aside leaf litter and look under grass tufts.

Pitfalls

Within the NBI plot and the 2002 burn area, we set a line of five pitfall traps 10 meters apart starting from a random point and continuing at a random compass bearing. Pitfalls were first set on 29 May 2007 and were emptied and reset every seven days until 21 August 2007 for a total of 840 trap-nights (one trap for one night). Each trap consisted of an eight-ounce canning jar with a 14 cm diameter funnel hot-glued to the screw-on top following a design used by Robert Edwards on Cape Cod. The trap was buried so the lip of the funnel was flush with ground level and was covered with half of a plastic four gallon temporary landscaping pot (cut longitudinally) to protect it from rain. We used propylene glycol in the traps.

We measured the height of five grass stems and five heath stems, estimated the percent cover of grass and heath, and counted the number of heath stems within a 3.14 m² area around each trap. We delineated the area by placing a one meter diameter hula-hoop on the ground centered on the trap.

Results

Within the NBI plot we caught 443 adult spiders representing 15 families and 69 species (Table 1) (Appendix A). Between 29 May 2007 and 14 August 2007 we logged 43 hours of hand collection among 15 collectors. The five additional pitfall traps in the 2002 burn site captured 334 spiders and added 17 species for a total of 777 adult spiders representing 18 families and 85 species within the entire SHCP area.

Table 1. Summary of the number of species captured at each site. We caught 85 species in the SHCP area and 69 species within the NBI plot.

Coll. Method	NBI plot				SHCP 2002 burn	Totals
	Hand Coll.	Pitfalls	Casual		Pitfalls	
			Beetsheet	Berlese		
#trapnights/Coll. hours	43	420	0.25 hrs.	13.6L	420	840 (trap nights)
# Adults	126	308	2	7	334	777
# Families	15	12	2	3	14	18
# Species	40	41	2	3	44	85
Subtotal # species	68		5		44	-
Total # species	69				44	-
Grand Total	85					

We caught significantly more females than males in hand collections and significantly more males than females in pitfalls within the NBI plot (paired, two tailed t-tests, $p \leq 0.000$ for both) (Fig. 1). The sex ratio for spiders from the pitfall traps at the 2002 burn site was just barely significantly skewed towards the males (paired, two tailed t-test, $p \leq 0.025$). Overall, within the SHCP, we caught 466 adult males, 302 adult females, and 9 identifiable immature spiders. We caught significantly more spiders per pitfall trap in June than both in July and August at both sites (Fig 2).

Figure 1. Sex ratio of spiders by collection method and site. Hand collecting only took place within the NBI plot. Significance values: * $p \leq 0.000$, * $p \leq 0.025$.**

Figure 2. Average number of spider captures in each month of sampling in pitfalls at the NBI plot and the 2002 burn site. Significantly more spiders were caught in June than in July or August. * $p \leq 0.000$**

Within the NBI plot, 54 percent (38/70) of the species are from the predominantly ground dwelling families Linyphiidae (13 species), Lycosidae (7), Thomisidae (6), Corinnidae (6) and Gnaphosidae (6). The other 46 percent of species represent families that actively hunt in vegetation like Salticidae (7 species), Philodromidae (4) and Clubionidae (4), or those that build webs in vegetation like Araneidae (5) and Theridiidae (4).

More species from the Linyphiidae (sheetweb weavers) were captured than from any other family. These are very, very small spiders with a diverse range of life histories. However, we caught more individual specimens from the Lycosidae (wolf spiders, 120 specimens) than any other family. The next most abundant families were the Gnaphosidae (78) and Thomisidae (crab spiders, 54).

Hand Collections

During the hand collections in the NBI plot, we caught most of the species we expected to find or have already caught in previous surveys at other sites. However, we caught several interesting and important species. We found one female *Larinia borealis*, an orb weaving spider that Kaston (1948) considers a rare species and which is on Emerton's list from 1930 (Emerton 1930). We also caught the sac spider *Cheiracanthium inclusum*, which is a native species. We had only previously found its non-native relative *Cheiracanthium mildei* which prefers living in buildings.

We collected seven species that are possible new records for Nantucket County (Table 2). We will not know for sure until the Emerton collection has been re-identified and catalogued based on the current classification system. See the 2007 Spider Inventory Summary Report for all county records (Mckenna-Foster and Beaton 2008a).

Table 2. Possible records for Nantucket County from the SHCP area.

Family	Species	Location	Capture Method
Araneidae	<i>Cyclosa conica</i>	SHCP NBI plot	Hand collection
Corinnidae	<i>Meriola decepta</i>	SHCP NBI plot/ 2002 burn site	Hand collect/ pitfall
Dictynidae	<i>Dictyna formidolosa</i>	2002 burn site	Pitfall
	<i>Emblyna cruciata</i>	SHCP NBI plot	Hand collect
	<i>Scotolathys pallidus</i>	SHCP NBI plot/ 2002 burn site	Pitfall
Gnaphosidae	<i>Micaria longispina</i>	SHCP NBI plot	Pitfall
Linyphiidae	<i>Ceraticelus bryantae</i>	SHCP NBI plot	Hand collect
	<i>Ceratinopsis atolma</i>	SHCP NBI plot	Hand collect
	<i>Masoncus arienus</i>	SHCP NBI plot	Pitfall
Lycosidae	<i>Hogna aspera</i>	2002 burn site	Pitfall
	<i>Schizocosa saltatrix</i>	SHCP NBI plot/ 2002 burn site	Pitfall
	<i>Trochosa ruricola</i>	2002 burn site	Pitfall
Salticidae	<i>Habronattus decorus</i>	SHCP NBI plot	Hand Collect
	<i>Habronattus viridipes</i>	SHCP NBI plot	Hand Collect
	<i>Talavera minuta</i>	SHCP NBI plot/ 2002 burn site	Pitfall

Pitfall traps

Traps in the NBI plot were heath predominated while those at the 2002 burn site were grass predominated (Table 3). NBI plot traps were surrounded by significantly more heath plants (71%) than the 2002 burn site (22%) (t-test, $p \leq 0.022$). Traps in the 2002 burn site were surrounded by significantly more grasses (77%) than those in the NBI plot (29%) (t-test, $p \leq 0.022$). Additionally, the grass height around the traps in the 2002 burn site was significantly higher (t-test, $p \leq 0.000$) than in the NBI plot and it had significantly fewer heath stems (t-test, $p \leq 0.011$). In the NBI plot, measured heath plants were predominantly low bush blueberry (*Vaccinium angustifolium*) and bayberry (*Myrica pensylvanica*) while in the 2002 burn site, measured plants were predominantly huckleberry (*Gaylussacia baccata*) and dewberry (*Rubus hispidus*). Another major difference between the two sites is that the 2002 burn area is only about 400 meters from coastal dunes while the NBI plot is about 800 meters.

Table 3. Vegetation characteristics from pitfall traps at the NBI plot and the 2002 burn site. The NBI plot had significantly more heath plants by area and count and shorter grass height.

	Avg. % Heath	Avg. % Grass	Avg Heath Ht. (cm)	Avg Grass Ht. (cm)	Avg. Heath Stem Count	Description
NBI plot	71±12	29±6.3	24±3.9	28±2.1	83±22	Heath predominated
2002 burn	22±6.3	77±12	24±3.6	50±2.6	23±17	Grass predominated

The pitfall traps set in the 2002 burn site captured an assemblage that is 84% similar to that from the biodiversity plot pitfall traps (Sorensen similarity). The 2002 burn site had 44 species while the NBI plot had 41 species and they shared 27 species (Table 1). We caught a total of 58 species between the sites. At each site there were three species that occurred in significantly higher numbers than at the other site (Table 4). There was no significant relationship between these species and the percent heath or grass cover, vegetation height or stem height.

Table 4. Six species showed significantly skewed distributions between the two pitfall sites. None showed significant relationships with vegetation characteristics around the traps.

Species	NBI Plot	2002 Burn Site
<i>Euryopis gertschi</i>	23 specimens	5 specimens
<i>Xusticus ferox</i>	17	5
<i>Zelotes laccus</i>	32	11
<i>Agroeca pratensis</i>	1	14
<i>Nerienne clathrata</i>	5	17
<i>Schizocosa bilineata</i>	8	56

At the 2002 burn site we caught one male specimen of the non-native wolf spider *Trochosa ruricola* which was introduced from Europe or Asia over 100 years ago and is slowly migrating westward (Prentice 2001). We also caught one male purseweb spider, *Sphodros niger*, an extremely cryptic tarantula species (Mckenna-Foster and Beaton 2008b).

Within the NBI plot, the pitfalls captured two species that are possible new county records and the 2002 burn site pitfalls captured three possible new records. Three more possible records, for a total of eight from the pitfall traps, were captured at both sites (Table 2).

Analysis of methods and inventory completeness

We completed 22 hours of sweep netting to catch 79 adult spiders and 21 hours of ground collecting to catch 47 adult spiders. We did not count immature spiders. On average, collectors completed 41 sweep events in one hour and there was no significant difference between first-time collectors and veteran collectors. Sweep netting captured significantly more spiders than ground collecting (4.1 to 2.6 spiders/hour respectively, two tailed independent t-test, $p \leq 0.024$). Using very rough calculations of the amount of actual area sampled, we estimate that sweep netting covered 0.11 ha and ground collection (without pitfalls) covered 0.05 ha for a total of 0.16 ha (see Appendix D for calculations).

Our main goal was to compile a species list for the NBI plot specifically as well as the rare sandplain grassland and heathland habitat in general. Factors that can indicate completeness are a high sampling intensity (# of specimens/# of species), a low number of singletons (species represented by only one specimen, usually around 30%, Coddington *et al.* 2007), and a logarithmic species richness curve that levels off at an asymptote (Coddington *et al.* 1991; Scharff *et al.* 2003). We calculated a sampling intensity of 6.4 (443/69) for the NBI plot and a sampling intensity of nine for the whole

SHCP area (777/85). Within the NBI plot we collected 26 singletons (37%) and within the entire SHCP area we collected 35 singletons (41%). All of these suggest our survey cannot be considered complete.

For spiders collected by hand, we created a species richness curve (Fig. 3) using Estimate S software (Colwell 2005). The curve is a plot of the number of specimens collected versus the accumulated number of species (randomized over 50 iterations) and the software produces several estimated curves based on various mathematical estimators. Ideally, the estimated and observed curves should level out relatively near each other at an asymptote, which represents the total number of species in the area (Scharff *et al.* 2003). Our curve does not level off. The Chao 1 estimator agrees with our final species list in suggesting that hand collections captured about half of the available species (40 out of 70) in the NBI plot. We cannot rely on the estimated curves as accurate species counts because our sample size (126 spiders) is too small.

Figure 3. Species richness curves for the NBI plot based on the number of spiders and the number of species caught at the site in hand collections. The Chao 1 and Jack estimators are estimated curves produced by the software. The curve for the number of species captured does not level off suggesting our inventory is incomplete.

Because we cannot equate the effort of hand collecting with pitfall trapping we created a separate species area curve with the pitfall data (Fig. 4). This curve is useful in

determining if the pitfall traps captured most of the available species and whether we set enough pitfalls to accurately sample the area. We only used pitfall data from the first week of June for both sites because this was the most successful time for pitfall trapping (Fig. 2) and by limiting the trapping period we eliminated the confounding factor of new species emerging part way through the dataset (some species emerge later in the summer). The average number of spiders per trap at the NBI plot and at the 2002 burn site was not significantly different for early June (two tailed ind. t-test, $p \leq 0.22$). Our data points do not level off in a way that would suggest our 10 pitfall traps caught most of the available species in the area that first week.

By extrapolating the curve we can estimate the optimal number of traps. Since the 1930's it has been assumed that one can do this by finding the point on the curve where an increase of 5% in the number of species is produced by a 10% increase in effort or area (Oosting 1956; Uetz and Unzicker 1976). On a best fit line for our data, we hit this point at 20 pitfall traps. This curve seems reasonable when compared with pitfall data from later weeks. In the first three weeks of June we caught 37 species from both sites but in the first week alone we caught 75 % (28/37) of the species. After the first week of trapping, it took twice the effort to catch the remaining nine species. Setting 20 traps during this time period should capture 92% (34/37) of the available species. Additionally, 10 pitfall traps set for three weeks can be broadly assumed to be equivalent to one week of 30 traps (ignoring temporal effects on species abundance). Our curve passes near the point created by this assumption of 30 traps and 37 species, (29,37) (Fig 4).

Figure 4. Estimating the required number of pitfall traps to capture most of the species available in the SHCP area. The x-axis is the number of pitfall traps for seven days. The large dark circle represents the optimal number of traps based on the point of the curve where a 10% increase in pitfall area results in only a 5% increase in the number of species. The X on the curve is close to the point where we see our data after three weeks of trapping—roughly equivalent to 30 traps for one week yielding 37 species.

Discussion

We estimate that our final list of 70 species for the SHCP NBI plot represents about 60-70% of the total species for two reasons: 1) we were not able to sample in the late fall when many orb-weaving and jumping spiders are mature and active and 2) our sampling effort was too small to catch more species. The former reason is likely to have had a more significant influence on our results. We know several more species occur at the site. Two species of *Argiope* (late fall orbweavers, Araneidae) and the extremely large Carolina Wolf spider (Lycosidae, *Hogna carolinensis*) probably occur on the site and, at the opposite end of the size spectrum, there are probably several more very tiny species of sheetweb spiders (Linyphiidae). However, our collection is a good representation of the early summer assemblage of spiders.

Looking at the 2002 burn site pitfall traps along with the NBI plot data, we estimate that a sandplain grassland and heathland mosaic has at least 85 species and this probably under-represents the total number of species for the same reasons listed above. Each site had three species that occurred at significantly higher abundances at one site compared to the other (Table 4). Whether they indicate a special habitat preference (e.g. heath over grass or proximity to beach dunes) is unclear and needs further study.

The high male sex ratios for the pitfall traps and the high female ratio for the hand collecting demonstrate the need for both methods in a species survey. The pitfalls catch males as they wander searching for females and the hand collecting catches females either in webs or in retreats with egg sacs.

Our original goal was to achieve a sampling intensity of 10 within the NBI plot. We reached a value of 6.4. Had we reached our goal of 60 hand collecting hours within the plot it would have only increased our sampling intensity to seven. For the SHCP area as a whole our sampling intensity of nine is much closer to our goal. Scharff *et al.* (2003) suggests a value of 30 for a hardwood forest while Toti *et al.* (2000) reported a fairly complete survey of a southern Appalachia heath bald with a value of 9.6. Because of the low plant structure in sandplain grassland and heathland compared to forests, a sampling intensity more near Toti *et al.* (2000) is probably acceptable. However, our sampling intensity is buoyed by the pitfall traps and to create a species richness curve with low error values we would need to reach a value of 10 solely with hand collection. We caught an average of 3.4 ± 0.56 spiders per hour hand collecting and to catch the 850 specimens required ($850/85 = 10$) we would need to ground search and sweep net for 250 hours ($850/3.4$). This is unrealistic for the limited resources available and the approach we have taken of combining pitfalls, hand collecting and casual collecting to infer an approximate number of species is a good substitute.

Data from this project will be important for future work concerning the conservation and management of sandplain grassland and heathland habitat. It provides us with enough information to make future research efficient and cost effective. For example, we now know that pitfall trapping in early June will catch the maximum number of spiders in the shortest amount of time (= high sampling intensity) and we know that setting 20 pitfall traps at this time will catch 92% of the available species in the area. Conceivably, a comparative study of spiders (and thus the local insect community) in sandplain grassland and heathland under different management strategies, or with different proximities to areas with high insecticide use, or different proximities to areas compromised by invasive plant species, can be completed based on one week of pitfall trapping in June.

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Map 1. Sampling locations in the Smooth Hummocks Coastal Preserve.

Appendix A

SHCP NBI

Plot

69 species, 8 unidentified, 25 singletons

443 specimens

Family	Genus	species	NumberSpecimens
Anyphaenidae	Hibana	gracilis	9
Araneidae	Acanthepeira	stellata	4
	Araneus	miniatus	1
	Cyclosa	conica	1
	Larinia	borealis	1
	Neoscona	arabesca	9
Clubionidae	Clubiona	johnsoni	16
	Clubiona	Morpho sp. A	6
	Clubiona	pikei	3
	Elaver	excepta	1
Corinnidae	Meriola	decepta	1
	Phrurolithus	similis	8
	Phruronellus	formica	3
	Phrurotimpus	alarius	4
	Phrurotimpus	borealis	3
	Phrurotimpus	minutus	10
Dictynidae	Emblyna	cruciata	1
	Scotolathys	pallidus	4
Gnaphosidae	Cesonia	bilineata	4
	Drassyllus	creolus	10
	Haplodrassus	signifer	21
	Micaria	longispina	2
	Zelotes	hentzi	7
	Zelotes	laccus	32
	Linyphiidae	Agyneta	Morpho sp. B
	Ceraticelus	bryantae	1
	Ceratinops	crenatus	1
	Ceratinopsis	atolma	1
	Grammonota	capitata	1
	Grammonota	pictilis	1
	Masoncus	arienus	1
	Neriene	clathrata	7
		Morpho sp.	
	No id	BA	1
		Morpho sp.	
	No id	BB	1
		Morpho sp.	
	No id	BC	1
		Morpho sp.	
	No id	XX	3
		Morpho sp.	
	No id	ZZ	1
Liocranidae	Agroeca	pratensis	1
Lycosidae	Hogna	helluo	5

	Pardosa	distincta	45
	Pardosa	saxatilis	55
	Rabidosa	rabida	3
	Schizocosa	avida	3
	Schizocosa	bilineata	8
	Schizocosa	saltatrix	1
Miturgidae	Cheiracanthium	inclusum	6
Oxyopidae	Oxyopes	salticus	5
Philodromidae	Philodromus	imbecillus	1
	Philodromus	placidus	1
	Thanatus	formicinus	6
	Tibellus	oblongus	5
Salticidae	Habronattus	decorus	1
	Habronattus	viridipes	2
	Hentzia	palmarum	9
	Marpissa	lineata	4
	Pelegrina	galathea	5
	Talavera	minuta	3
	Zygoballus	rufipes	1
Tetragnathidae	Tetragnatha	laboriosa	9
Theridiidae	Emertonella	gertschi	1
	Euryopis	gertschi	23
	Euryopis	Morpho sp. A	1
	Theridion	differens	1
Thomisidae	Ozyptila	americana	14
	Xysticus	alboniger	3
	Xysticus	bicuspis	5
	Xysticus	ferox	19
	Xysticus	funestus	2
	Xysticus	luctans	11

Appendix B

SHCP 2002 Burn site

44 species, 6 unidentified, 17 singletons

334 specimens

Family	Genus	species	NumberSpecies
Araneidae	Acanthepeira	stellata	1
Atypidae	Sphodros	niger	1
Clubionidae	Clubiona	Morpho sp. A	1
Corinnidae	Castianeira	longipalpa	1
	Meriola	decepta	4
	Phrurolithus	similis	3
	Phruronellus	formica	1
	Phrurotimpus	borealis	2
	Phrurotimpus	minutus	7
Dictynidae	Dictyna	formidolosa	1
	Scotolathys	pallidus	3
Gnaphosidae	Cesonia	bilineata	2
	Drassyllus	creolus	17
	Haplodrassus	signifer	29
	Sergiolus	Morpho sp. A	2
	Zelotes	hentzi	13
	Zelotes	laccus	11
Hahniidae	Hahnia	cinerea	1
	Neoantistea	agilis	1
Linyphiidae	Neriere	clathrata	17
	No id	Morpho sp. WW	2
	No id	Morpho sp. YY	2
	No id	Morpho sp. Z	1
Liocranidae	Agroeca	pratensis	14
Lycosidae	Allocosa	funerea	1
	Arctosa	rubicunda	1
	Hogna	aspera	1
	Hogna	carolinensis	1
	Hogna	helluo	7
	Pardosa	distincta	27
	Pardosa	saxatilis	45
	Rabidosa	punctulata	1
	Schizocosa	avida	1
	Schizocosa	bilineata	56
	Schizocosa	saltatrix	2
	Trochosa	ruricola	1
Philodromidae	Thanatus	formicinus	2
Salticidae	Talavera	minuta	1
Theridiidae	Euryopis	gertschi	5
	Euryopis	Morpho sp. B	2
Thomisidae	Ozyptila	americana	20
	Xysticus	alboniger	3
	Xysticus	ferox	5
	Xysticus	luctans	15

Appendix C

Entire SHCP Area

85 species, 12 unidentified, 34 singletons

777 specimens

Family	Genus	species	NumberSpecimens
Anyphaenidae	Hibana	gracilis	9
Araneidae	Acanthepeira	stellata	5
	Araneus	miniatus	1
	Cyclosa	conica	1
	Larinia	borealis	1
	Neoscona	arabesca	9
Atypidae	Sphodros	niger	1
Clubionidae	Clubiona	johnsoni	16
	Clubiona	sp. A	7
	Clubiona	pikei	3
	Elaver	excepta	1
Corinnidae	Castianeira	longipalpa	1
	Meriola	decepta	5
	Phrurolithus	similis	11
	Phruronellus	formica	4
	Phrurotimpus	alarius	4
	Phrurotimpus	borealis	5
	Phrurotimpus	minutus	17
Dictynidae	Dictyna	formidolosa	1
	Emblyna	cruciata	1
	Scotolathys	pallidus	7
Gnaphosidae	Cesonia	bilineata	6
	Drassyllus	creolus	27
	Haplodrassus	signifer	50
	Micaria	longispina	2
	Sergiolus	decoratus	2
	Zelotes	hentzi	20
	Zelotes	laccus	43
Hahniidae	Hahnia	cinerea	1
	Neoantistea	agilis	1
Linyphiidae	Agyneta	sp. B	3
	Ceraticelus	bryantae	1
	Ceratinops	crenatus	1
	Ceratinopsis	atolma	1
	Grammonota	capitata	1
	Grammonota	pictilis	1
	Masoncus	arienus	1
	Neriene	clathrata	24
	No id	sp. BA	1
	No id	sp. BB	1
	No id	sp. BC	1
	No id	sp. WW	2
	No id	sp. XX	3
No id	sp. YY	2	

	No id	sp. Z	1
	No id	sp. ZZ	1
Liocranidae	Agroeca	pratensis	15
Lycosidae	Allocosa	funerea	1
	Arctosa	rubicunda	1
	Hogna	aspera	1
	Hogna	carolinensis	1
	Hogna	helluo	12
	Pardosa	distincta	72
	Pardosa	saxatilis	100
	Rabidosa	punctulata	1
	Rabidosa	rabida	3
	Schizocosa	avida	4
	Schizocosa	bilineata	64
	Schizocosa	saltatrix	3
	Trochosa	ruricola	1
Miturgidae	Cheiracanthium	inclusum	6
Oxyopidae	Oxyopes	salticus	5
Philodromidae	Philodromus	imbecillus	1
	Philodromus	placidus	1
	Thanatus	formicinus	8
	Tibellus	oblongus	5
Salticidae	Habronattus	decorus	1
	Habronattus	viridipes	2
	Hentzia	palmarum	9
	Marpissa	lineata	3
	Pelegrina	galathea	5
	Talavera	minuta	5
	Zygoballus	rufipes	1
Tetragnathidae	Tetragnatha	laboriosa	9
Theridiidae	Emertonella	gertschi	1
	Euryopis	gertschi	28
	Euryopis	sp. A	1
	Euryopis	sp. B	2
	Theridion	differens	1
Thomisidae	Ozyptila	americana	34
	Xysticus	alboniger	6
	Xysticus	bicuspis	5
	Xysticus	ferox	24
	Xysticus	funestus	2
	Xysticus	luctans	26

Appendix D

Collection Area Calculations

Sweep Netting:

$$(0.38\text{m, Diameter of net})(5 \text{ sweeps/sweep event})(1 \text{ m/sweep})(\text{No. of sweep events})$$

$$=\text{Area (m}^2\text{)}$$

Ground Collecting:

$$(0.5\text{m, width of collecting line})(\text{length of collecting line})$$

$$=\text{Area (m}^2\text{)}$$

CollectionID	No. adults spiders	Length (m)	Sweep Events	Width (m)	Total area (sq. m)
SHCP10bGRND1	1	40		0.5	20
SHCP10bGRND3	4	45		0.5	22.5
SHCP1aGRND1	1	70		0.5	35
SHCP1aGRND2	2	70		0.5	35
SHCP2aGRND1	1	40		0.5	20
SHCP2aGRND2	2	70		0.5	35
SHCP2aGRND3	4	50		0.5	25
SHCP2bGRND	7	70		0.5	35
SHCP3aGRND1	1	50		0.5	25
SHCP3aGRND3	1	80		0.5	40
SHCP4aGRND2	1	25		0.5	12.5
SHCP4bGRND1	1	90		0.5	45
SHCP4bGRND2	5	80		0.5	40
SHCP5bGRND	2	50		0.5	25
SHCP6bGRND1	4	80		0.5	40
SHCP6bGRND2	4	80		0.5	40
SHCP9bGRND	1	50		0.5	25
SHCP10bSWP1	2	40	37	1.905	70.485
SHCP10bSWP2	3	40	29	1.905	55.245
SHCP10bSWP3	2	40	34	1.905	64.77
SHCP10bSWP4	2	40	17	1.905	32.385
SHCP11bSWP1	9	75	64	1.905	121.92
SHCP1aSWP	1	70	30	1.905	57.15
SHCP1bSWP	2	100	46	1.905	87.63
SHCP2aSWP1	7	60	30	1.905	57.15
SHCP2aSWP3	5	50	35	1.905	66.675
SHCP3aSWP1	2	60	44	1.905	83.82
SHCP3aSWP2	1	35	53	1.905	100.965
SHCP3aSWP3	2	35	39	1.905	74.295

SHCP4aSWP1	1	50	47	1.905	89.535
SHCP4aSWP3	3	40	32	1.905	60.96
SHCP9bSWP2	7	50	56	1.905	106.68
			Total		1649.665
			Ground		520
			Sweep events		1129.665